

ESTIMATE SOME OF CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND POTENTIAL HEALTH RISK OF HEAVY METALS IN TOOTHPASTE SAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the physicochemical properties and heavy metal content of commercially available toothpaste products in Derna City, Libya. Ten toothpaste samples, including two specifically formulated for children, were randomly collected and analyzed for pH, sodium (Na), potassium (K), and concentrations of selected heavy metal contents (Fe, Zn, Pb, Cd, Ni, Cr, and Cu). Analytical techniques such as atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) and flame photometry were employed. The results revealed that pH values ranged from 5.24 to 7.79, with 40% of the samples exhibiting acidic pH. Sodium concentrations ranged from 2280 to 3900 mg/L, exceeding the recommended limit in several samples, while potassium levels varied between 5 and 62 mg/L. Heavy metals were detected in all samples, with some (particularly Pb, Cd, Ni, and Cr) approaching or exceeding permissible limits in certain cases. Health risk assessment, performed using the Target Hazard Quotient (THQ) and Hazard Index (HI) models,

indicated no significant non-carcinogenic risk (THQ and HI values < 1). However, the presence of trace amounts of potentially harmful metals suggests that there should be routine quality monitoring and regulatory oversight, especially for children's oral care products. The findings emphasize the need for continuous assessment to ensure toothpaste safety and compliance with international health standards.

KEYWORDS: *Toothpaste, Heavy metals, pH, Sodium, Target Hazard Quotient (THQ).*

INTRODUCTION

Toothpaste plays a crucial role in oral hygiene by providing protection against oral bacteria, maintaining fresh breath, and offering fluoride-based defense against dental caries. Additionally, it contributes to teeth whitening and helps prevent bacterial infections within the oral cavity. In certain cases, various metallic elements have been incorporated into toothpaste formulations to enhance specific properties (Khan et al., 2021). Toothpaste, as a multifunctional oral care product, is widely used to clean teeth, prevent tartar buildup, provide fluoride protection, freshen breath, and improve dental aesthetics. The diverse benefits of these products have driven their extensive global demand and widespread daily use (Orisakwe et al., 2016). Fluoride is the most closely monitored ingredient due to health risks, while heavy metals in toothpaste have received limited attention. Their presence is often attributed to contamination or intentional addition as preservative agents to improve product stability under heat and extended storage conditions (Valentine et al., 2022).

In addition to heavy metal content, the pH value of toothpaste plays a significant role in maintaining oral health. An optimal pH range helps in minimizing enamel erosion and controlling bacterial. Moreover, the sodium content, which influences the electrical conductivity of toothpaste, is also of interest as excessive sodium intake from oral care products can contribute to systemic exposure. In toothpaste formulations, sodium is commonly present in several compounds, each serving a specific function: Sodium fluoride (NaF): Used as a fluoride source to help prevent dental caries. Sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS): Functions as a surfactant and foaming agent to help distribute the toothpaste in the mouth. Sodium bicarbonate (baking soda): Acts as a mild abrasive and whitening agent, and helps neutralize acids. Sodium saccharin: Used as an artificial sweetener to improve taste (Vranic et al., 2004). Heavy metals, naturally present in the environment at trace concentrations, can become toxic and hazardous when raised above recommended limits. Human exposure can occur through contaminated food and water, personal care products, industrial emissions, and traffic pollutants, posing significant risks (Ghaedi et al., 2005). Popular public health approach fluorinated toothpaste is readily available and accepted economically. However, heavy metals in toothpaste manufacturing can be contaminated through three main pathways: absorbing by plant leaves during cultivation, unintentional cross-contamination during manufacturing and processing, and intentionally adding heavy metals as active therapeutic

agents. Heavy metals are micro-pollutants with high density and toxicity, and their persistence, bio accumulative potential, and harmful effects necessitate strict monitoring. Human exposure to these metals can occur through direct and indirect sources, leading to neurological impairments, renal dysfunction, and increased cancer risk (Ideriahet al., 2016). Heavy metals can unintentionally contaminate toothpaste products during production processes, particularly in herbal formulations. These metals can disrupt key physiological systems, such as the nervous, cardiovascular, and digestive systems. Lead, known for its carcinogenic effects, is particularly dangerous for pregnant women. Chromium exposure can cause skin ulcers and kidney damage. Cadmium can impair the kidneys, liver, lungs, and nervous system. Mercury is hazardous due to its reaction with biological chemicals. Nickel, valued for its durability in dental alloys, can be released into the oral cavity through toothpaste use. Zinc, often used in toothpaste, has been shown to reduce halitosis with consistent use (Khan et al., 2021). Health risk assessments such as the Target Hazard Quotient (THQ) are widely applied to estimate the potential non-carcinogenic risks associated with the ingestion of heavy metals through consumer products (USEPA, 2011). A THQ value less than one suggests no significant health risk, whereas a value above one indicates potential health concerns (USEPA. 2011). To comply with health regulations and the complex nature of toothpaste formulations, sensitive and selective analytical techniques like atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) are crucial. Successful application requires careful sample preparation protocols tailored to toothpaste's chemical makeup (Popova & Marinova., 2007). This study aims to evaluate the composition of ten commercially available toothpaste samples from the local market in Derna city. The specific objectives of this research can be summarized as follows: To measurement the pH of the tooth paste samples. To determine the contents of sodium and potassium. Determination the heavy metals contents in tooth paste samples. Calculate the Health Risk Assessment (Target Hazard Quotient - THQ) & Hazard Index HI. This study aims to evaluate the composition of ten commercially available toothpaste samples from the local market in Derna city. The specific objectives of this research can be summarized as follows: To measurement the pH of the tooth paste samples. To determine the contents of sodium and potassium. Determination the heavy metals contents in tooth paste samples. Calculate the Health Risk Assessment (Target Hazard Quotient - THQ) & Hazard Index HI.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material

Experimental Procedure

This chapter including the sampling of Tooth Paste, the contents of (pH, Sodium, Potassium and heavy metals) were measured according to standard methods. Analytical grade reagents were used. Distilled deionized water was used for the solution preparations. All solutions were stored in polyethene bottles prior to analysis.

Sampling

A total of ten commercially available toothpaste brands were randomly selected from local markets in Derna city/Libya in January 2025. The samples were covering a range of commonly used formulations for adults and children. The samples were labeled TP-1 to TP-10. Among these samples (TP-1–8) were general and two were children toothpaste (TP-9 and TP-10). Each toothpaste sample was labeled accordingly and stored at room temperature in their original packaging prior to analysis. The types of samples were given in Table (2.1):

Table (2.1) The types of tooth paste samples.

Sample ID	Sample No		Chemical formulation	Color
TP-1	Colgate		Cream	White
TP-2	Closeup		Gel	Light green
TP-3	Orbil life		Cream	White
TP-4	Crest		Cream	White

TP-5	Miswak		Cream	White
TP-6	Signal		Cream	White with pink
TP-7	Miswak gel		Gel	Pale yellow
TP-8	Dabur herbl		Cream	White
TP-9	Pro namel (kids)		Cream	Pink
TP-10	(kids) colgate		Cream	Blue

Sample preparations

Dried toothpastes (1g each) were soaked in Teflon crucible with 50 ml water for 24 h. The mixture was filtered into 100ml volumetric flask, the residue washed thoroughly and the filtrate made up to volume with deionized water.

Digestion of samples

To detect heavy metals, samples were digested. Subsequently, one gram of tooth paste samples were placed in a round bottom flask, and a mixture of 10 ml of deionized water is added and 5 mL concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 5 mL perchloric acid (HClO₄) was added. The mixture was heated on a hot plate for one hour until complete digestion occurred and a clear solution was obtained. After cooling, the digested solution was filtered and diluted to a final volume of 100 mL with deionized water. The concentrations of heavy Metals were measured by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) at central lab of Faculty of Science, Omar Al Mukhtar University.

Figure (1): The steps for the digestion of tooth paste samples.

Health Risk Assessment (Target Hazard Quotient - THQ) & Hazard Index HI

The potential non-carcinogenic health risks associated with the ingestion of heavy metals from toothpaste use were assessed by calculating the Target Hazard Quotient (THQ) for each heavy metal according to the USEPA (2011) guidelines, using the formula:

$$THQ = \frac{EF \times ED \times IR \times C}{RfD \times BW \times AT}$$

Where

EF = Exposure frequency (365 days/year), **ED** = Exposure duration (80 years), **IR** = Daily ingestion rate of toothpaste (0.0005 Kg/day for adults), **C** = Heavy metal concentration in toothpaste (mg/kg), **RfD** = Oral reference dose for each metal (mg/kg/day), **BW** = Average body weight (60 kg for adults), **AT** = Averaging time (ED × 365 days). A THQ value less than 1 indicates no significant health risk, while a value equal to or greater than 1 suggests potential health concerns.

$$HI \text{ (Hazard Index)} = \sum THQ_{\text{all heavy metals}}$$

where, HI = Hazard Index

THQ= Target Hazard Quotient of all heavy metals.

pH value

It was measured on 1 percent solution of the sample in water using (A HANNA PH meter), incorporating a glass cell and reference electrode. Buffer tablets of pH 4, 7 and 9 were used to calibrate the pH meter during measurements.

Sodium and Potassium

Concentrations for (Na and K) were determined using a Flame Photometer (type, JENWAY) at central lab of Institute of Agricultural Sciences in Derna.

2.2.6. Software programming

Excel was used for draw the Figures in this study.

RESULTS

The results obtained in this study describing as following:

pH Value

The pH values of the analyzed toothpaste samples ranged from 5.24 to 7.79. The average pH of toothpaste samples was detected 6.887. The maximum and minimum pH was found 7.79 ± 0.40 and 5.24 ± 0.28 in Tp-3 and TP-10. forty percent of the samples were acidic pH, and 60% of the samples were slightly alkaline.

Table (1): pH Values, Electrical Conductivity and TDS of the Analyzed Toothpaste Samples.

Sample	PH Value	Electrical Conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)	TDS
TP-1	6.88	1215	850.5
TP-2	7.05	1938	1356.6
TP-3	7.78	1652	1156.4
TP-4	6.91	1955	1368.5
TP-5	7.23	1860	1302
TP-6	7.19	1845	1291.5
TP-7	5.55	1506	1054.2
TP-8	7.25	1946	1362.2
TP-9	7.79	1510	1057
TP-10	5.24	1512	1058.4
Mean	6.887	1693.9	1185.73
Max	7.79	1955	1368.5
Min	5.24	1215	850.5

Figure (1): The horizontal distribution pH Values in tooth paste samples.

Sodium Content

The analysis of sodium concentrations in the tested toothpaste samples revealed values ranging from 2280 mg/L to 3900 mg/L. The highest concentration was recorded in Sample TP-5 (3900 mg/L), while the lowest was detected in Sample TP-1 (2280 mg/L). The average sodium concentration across all samples was approximately 3336 mg/L.

Table (3.2): Contents of Sodium in the samples of Tooth paste.

Sample	Na mg/L
TP-1	2280
TP-2	3480
TP-3	3800
TP-4	3600
TP-5	3900
TP-6	3600
TP-7	2800
TP-8	3700
TP-9	3600
TP-10	2600
Mean	3336
±SD	561.72
Max	3900
Min	2280

Figure (2): The horizontal distribution of Sodium in tooth paste samples.

Potassium

The analysis of potassium concentrations in the tested toothpaste samples revealed values ranging from 5 mg/L to 62 mg/L. The highest concentration was recorded in Sample TP-3 (62 mg/L), while the lowest was detected in Sample TP-10 (5 mg/L). The average potassium concentration across all samples was approximately 19.2 mg/L.

Table (3): Contents of potassium in the samples of Tooth paste.

Sample	K mg/L
TP-1	13
TP-2	16
TP-3	62
TP-4	13
TP-5	24
TP-6	13
TP-7	8
TP-8	27
TP-9	11
TP-10	5
Mean	19.2
SD	16.45
Max	62
Min	5

Fig (3): The horizontal distribution of Sodium in tooth paste samples.

Heavy Metal Concentrations

The concentrations of heavy metals (Fe, Zn, Pb, Cd, Ni, Cr, and Cu) in the toothpaste samples are presented in Table (3.4).

Table (4): The contents of heavy metals in tooth paste samples.

Sample code	Pb mg/L	Cd mg/L	Cu mg/L	Zn mg/L	Ni mg/L	Fe mg/L	Cr mg/L
TP-1	0.04	0.027	0.729	1.657	0.012	0.064	0.03
TP-2	0.042	0.044	0.085	2.754	0.025	0.099	0.055
TP-3	0.048	0.076	0.326	2.404	0.081	0.029	0.074
TP-4	0.001	0.006	0.224	1.088	0.033	0.076	0.056
TP-5	0.035	0.059	0.06	0.916	0.084	0.038	0.013
TP-6	0.047	0.092	0.49	2.18	0.022	0.043	0.08
TP-7	0.022	0.01	0.999	2.88	0.035	0.046	0.068
TP-8	0.003	0.06	0.575	1.427	0.063	0.013	0.051
TP-9	0.009	0.062	0.712	0.665	0.096	0.042	0.037
TP-10	0.032	0.01	0.497	1.574	0.082	0.074	0.091
Mean	0.0279	0.0446	0.4697	1.7545	0.0533	0.0524	0.0555
Max	0.048	0.092	0.999	2.88	0.096	0.099	0.091
Min	0.001	0.006	0.06	0.665	0.012	0.013	0.013

Figure 4: The contents of heavy metals in the studied toothpaste samples.

Figure (5): The values of lead and cadmium in tooth paste samples.

Figure (6): The values of zinc and copper in tooth paste samples.

Figure (3.7): The values of Ni, Fe and Cr in tooth paste samples.

Health Risk Assessment (THQ and HI)**Table (3.4): Represent the values of THQ of the mean of the estimated heavy metals.**

Heavy metal	THQ
Cr	0.0001543
Fe	0.0000005654
Ni	0.0000222
Zn	0.0000489
Cu	0.0000979
Cd	0.0003717
Pb	0.0000581

$$HI = \sum THQ_{for\ all\ heavy\ metals} = 0.0006569$$

DISCUSSION

The pH values of the toothpaste samples range from 5.24 to 7.79, with an average of 6.887. This indicates that some samples are slightly acidic, while others are neutral to slightly alkaline. pH plays a crucial role in maintaining oral health, as excessively acidic toothpaste may erode enamel, whereas alkaline formulations could help neutralize acid in the mouth. The extreme values (5.24 and 7.79) suggest variability in formulation. Highly acidic pastes may contain ingredients aimed at plaque removal, while alkaline pastes might include antibacterial agents. The samples fall within the acceptable range, though the lowest pH (5.24) is slightly below the recommended minimum, which may indicate a higher acidity that could contribute to enamel erosion. The electrical conductivity values vary from 1215 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 1955 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, with an average of 1693.9 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. EC represents the ionic strength of the toothpaste, which is directly linked to its mineral and salt content. Higher EC values (closer to 1955 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) may indicate a greater presence of fluoride, calcium, or phosphate ions, essential for strengthening enamel and reducing the risk of cavities. In addition, TDS measures the total concentration of dissolved substances, including abrasives and detergents. TDS values in this study range from 850.5 mg/L to 1368.5 mg/L, averaging 1185.73 mg/L. The variability suggests differences in abrasive content, which influences cleaning efficiency and tooth surface.

According to (Khan et al. 2021), sodium concentrations in certain toothpaste samples were detected at levels exceeding the permissible limit of 2000 mg/L, as established by the US Patent. This elevation is likely attributed to the formulation components, particularly the presence of sodium fluoride, sodium bicarbonate, and sodium lauryl sulfate. Therefore, the

sodium concentrations identified in this study are considered higher than 2000 mg/L. However, it is noteworthy that Samples TP-3, TP-5, TP-8, and TP-9 exhibited relatively higher sodium levels (>3600 mg/L), which could potentially contribute to elevated daily sodium exposure, especially among populations using toothpaste multiple times daily. The resulting heavy metals were detected within acceptable values in all examined toothpaste samples, indicating no toxicity concerns and possible advantages: Copper (Cu): Concentrations ranged from 0.06 – 0.999 mg/L with a mean of 0.4697 mg/L. All samples fall within acceptable levels, suggesting that copper is present in safe amounts. Additionally, copper may contribute to antibacterial properties, supporting oral hygiene. Zinc (Zn): Concentrations varied between 0.665 – 2.88 mg/L, with a mean of 1.7545 mg/L. All samples comply with international safety standards. Zinc is recognized for its antimicrobial effects, which can enhance oral health and reduce bacterial proliferation. Iron (Fe): Found in concentrations ranging from 0.013 – 0.099 mg/L, with a mean of 0.0524 mg/L. All values remain within safe limits, confirming that iron content in the toothpaste samples does not pose toxicity concerns.

On the other hand, certain samples revealed concentrations of heavy metals that exceeded permissible limits, necessitating further monitoring and assessment due to potential health hazards such as Lead (Pb): Concentrations ranged from 0.001 – 0.048 mg/L, with a mean of 0.0279 mg/L. While all samples meet WHO and FDA standards, sample TP-3 (0.048 mg/L) is close to the upper WHO limit, indicating the need for careful regulation to prevent exposure beyond safe levels. Cadmium (Cd): Concentrations varied from 0.006 – 0.092 mg/L, with a mean of 0.0446 mg/L. Some samples exceeded safe limits, particularly TP-6 (0.092 mg/L), which raises concerns regarding potential chronic toxicity due to long-term exposure. Nickel (Ni): Concentrations ranged from 0.012 – 0.096 mg/L, with a mean of 0.0533 mg/L. Sample TP-9 (0.096 mg/L) exceeds WHO limits, posing risks of hypersensitivity reactions and potential toxicity with prolonged exposure. Chromium (Cr): Concentrations varied from 0.013 – 0.091 mg/L, with a mean of 0.0555 mg/L. Several samples exceed WHO standards, particularly TP-10 (0.091 mg/L), indicating a potential toxicity risk associated with frequent usage. Even though they include heavy metals including lead, cadmium, nickel, and chromium, TP-9 and TP-10 toothpaste products are designed for children. Lead exposure may damage mental development, causing difficulties with learning, reduce IQ, attention deficits, and developmental delays. Cadmium exposure can cause kidney damage, bone demineralization, and weaken the immune system, making children more susceptible to

infections. It is also classified as a carcinogen, increasing the risk of cancer. Nickel exposure can trigger skin allergies, causing rashes, itching, and dermatitis, especially in sensitive individuals. Over time, ingestion may contribute to gastrointestinal distress and potential toxicity. Chromium exposure, particularly hexavalent chromium (Cr VI), is highly toxic and can cause DNA damage, increasing cancer risk. It may lead to respiratory issues and skin irritation, especially in children with sensitive skin. Prolonged ingestion of chromium can affect liver and kidney function, leading to long-term health complications (Balali *et al.*, 2021). Although the current health risk assessment based on THQ values indicates no significant non-carcinogenic risk, the presence of trace amounts of potentially toxic metals underscores the importance of routine quality assessments. Particular attention should be given to Pb and Cr concentrations, which approached the permissible limits in some samples.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that toothpaste composition plays a fundamental role in maintaining oral health, with pH levels being a key determinant of enamel integrity. A pH above 7 is recommended to create a balanced oral environment, supporting salivary health and inhibiting harmful bacterial growth. Additionally, excessive chemical additives in toothpaste formulations may contribute to adverse dental and systemic effects, underscoring the necessity for careful regulation. Moreover, the presence of sodium (Na) and potassium (K) in toothpaste requires vigilant monitoring due to their potential health implications. While sodium compounds aid in preventing dental caries, excessive exposure particularly in children may lead to dental fluorosis, compromising enamel strength and appearance. Similarly, individuals suffering from kidney failure or cardiovascular disease must exercise caution, as potassium-containing compounds may disrupt electrolyte balance, potentially exacerbating renal and cardiovascular conditions. Furthermore, the heavy metal composition of toothpaste formulations necessitates stringent oversight to ensure safety. While elements such as copper, zinc, and iron contribute positively to oral health, metals such as lead, cadmium, nickel, and chromium pose toxicity risks that require regulatory intervention. Consequently, periodic quality assessments and strict regulatory compliance are imperative to safeguard consumer health and maintain product reliability. The calculated THQ and HI values for all detected heavy metals were below one, indicating no significant non-carcinogenic health risk from regular toothpaste use. These findings highlight the importance of continuous research and regulatory enforcement to ensure the safe formulation of toothpaste products. Future studies should focus on refining ingredient safety standards

and optimizing formulations to promote oral health without compromising overall well-being.

Recommendation

Future research should focus on integrating Graphite Atomic Structure and Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) techniques to enhance the accuracy of heavy metal detection in oral care products. Utilizing graphite electrodes can improve electrochemical sensitivity, while ICP-MS and ICP-OES offer precise quantification of toxic elements such as arsenic and mercury, ensuring adherence to regulatory standards. Additionally, extended risk assessments should be conducted to evaluate the cumulative effects of prolonged exposure, particularly concerning carcinogenic risks and electrolyte imbalances in individuals with pre-existing health conditions. Public awareness initiatives must also be prioritized to educate consumers on the importance of selecting certified and approved oral care products, reinforcing the necessity of strict quality control measures and continuous regulatory oversight. These efforts will contribute to a comprehensive approach toward ensuring both consumer safety and the integrity of oral health formulations.

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